

Implementation of a deep learning-based tool for automatic Cardiac Magnetic Resonance planning

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Cardiac Magnetic Resonance (CMR) is the gold standard technique for evaluating myocardial function and detecting myocardial scar. However, it requires complex and time-consuming planning. We aim to develop a deep-learning tool to automatically generate CMR views (SAX, 2CH, 3CH and 4CH) from a volumetric acquisition by estimating their defining vectors, thereby reducing operator dependency and examination time. We trained a 3DCNN with a dataset comprised of scout 3D acquisitions (288x288x113) from 120 subjects and corresponding set of vector coordinates defining the relevant view planes selected by an experienced operator. Volumes and labels were normalised and the former resized and cropped (70x70x50) to a region around the heart to decrease memory usage. We tested different network architectures: varying number of 3DConv layers and filters on the feature extraction block, varying number of dense units and layers on the fully connected regression block. Results are promising (fig.1), but overfitting occurs indicating the need for regularisation during training, data augmentation to steer the network towards invariance to the heterogeneity in MRI volumes and/or changes in architecture. Residual learning based CNNs and UNET architectures will be implemented, as they have been shown to provide good results at similar tasks [1,2].

Figure 1: (A) Schematic of the model's pipeline; (B) Examples of successful and unsuccessful test set predictions by one of the trained models with respective metrics (displacement and angulation errors).

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References

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